

Proof-of-vote, validators selected by people-vote

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ABSTRACT: Proof-of-vote is a third generation of the Nakamoto consensus. With proof-of-vote, validators compete for people-votes, using proof-of-suffrage given by proof-of-person, and authorize transactions based on authority delegated by the consensus mechanism, just like proof-of-work or proof-of-stake. This logical conclusion of the Nakamoto consensus allows a “nation” of people to secure their own ledger, the equivalent of representative democracy for distributed ledger technology.

Introduction

The Nakamoto consensus is a majority consensus system based on popular vote. What distinguishes the different variations of Nakamoto consensus algorithms (such as proof-of-work, proof-of-stake, or proof-of-vote) is how voting rights are allocated.

Proof-of-stake VS proof-of-vote

Overall, in a proof-of-stake network at any given time, you could remove all coins from all validators, replace those with people-votes in exact same quantity and distribution, and it would operate identically. The only difference is that the people voting get a share of the transaction fees.

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Secret votes

It is trivial to have secret votes. People give their validator a signed proof that they voted for them, incl. a nonce. The nonce is publicly incremented each time a person alters their vote. If a person provides secret signatures to two validators with the same nonce, and they both submit the evidence when the person is selected in the validator random cycle, then neither gets to publish a block. The rule for skipping a validator is applied (the hash of the random number is used), and enforced by the other validators who saw the proof.

Random majority vote

Besides the hash onion system used by validators, it is easy to add another mechanism, that periodically forces the validator hash onion system to randomly scramble the sequence it generates. This mechanism then means that any validator that submitted hash onion before the “adjustment”, is provably honest.

The mechanism ideally used for that, is “random majority vote”, a protocol that allows the population to generate a random number. It relies on a form of majority vote, but, no one can control what they vote for. They can only control that their vote is random, and know that the vote of every other person is random.

This is possible by using a commit-reveal scheme, where votes are committed before the votes in the previous period have been revealed. The random number generated by majority vote each period, is used to “mutate” the votes in the next period. This mechanism needs to be initialized with a random seed only once, and then continuously generates random numbers.

Votes contribute randomness to “generators”. There are as many generators as there are people, and the probability that some generator gets k “hits” is $e^{-1/k!}$. The generator that gets the most “hits”, i.e., a majority vote, wins.